
Design of small ducted propulsor for rear-fuselage boundary layer ingestion

The potential benefits of designing for conical flow

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ABSTRACT

A CFD-based design study for ducted Boundary-Layer Ingesting (BLI) propulsion is presented, which focusses on BLI engines which are small enough to operate well within the boundary and thus do not ingest air at free-stream Mach number at their design condition. Such designs are expected to require different design rules than either conventional underwing nacelles or larger BLI engines which ingest most of the boundary layer. Using a flexible parametric geometry definition and RANS CFD process for an axisymmetric propulsive fuselage, a parametric study finds a considerable benefit to aligning the fan cowl with the conical flow present at the boattail of the fuselage, and finds multiple further ways to improve on configurations which mimic the shape of underwing engines. The analysis includes installation effects but excludes the efficiency of the fan itself, and finds a design which requires 2.1% less power than the more conventional baseline design, and 2.3% less power than the theoretical limit for an engine operating on freestream inflow.

NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

<i>APPU</i>	Auxiliary Power and Propulsion Unit	<i>EPR</i>	Exhaust (total) Pressure Ratio
<i>BLI</i>	Boundary Layer Ingestion	<i>FPR</i>	Fan (total) Pressure Ratio
<i>CFD</i>	Computational Fluid Dynamics	<i>IPF</i>	Installed Propulsive Force
<i>CST</i>	Class-Shape Transformation	<i>IPR</i>	Inlet (total) Pressure Ratio
		<i>SLS</i>	Sea Level Static

Symbols

A	area	v_{in}	(expanded) intake air velocity
F'_N	overall net thrust	v_{jet}	(expanded) jet velocity
i_{cowl}	geometrical fan cowl conicity	v_∞	free-stream velocity
l	length	β	boat-tail angle
M	Mach number	Δv	momentum increase caused by propulsor
\dot{m}	massflow through the propulsor	η_{Froude}	Froude (propulsive) efficiency
NVF	Net vehicle force	Φ_{inst}	Installed propulsive force (IPF)
P_{fan}	power applied by the fan	Θ	tangent angle on conical surface
P_K	power required to cause Δv		
r	radius		

Suffixes

<i>bare</i>	bare fuselage	<i>inst</i>	installed
<i>cone</i>	fuselage tailcone	<i>intake</i>	intake
<i>exhaust</i>	exhaust	<i>low</i>	(fan) hub side
<i>fan</i>	fan	<i>out</i>	downstream fan face
<i>fus</i>	fuselage	<i>plug</i>	exhaust plug
<i>h</i>	(fan) hub side	<i>t</i>	(fan) tip side
<i>in</i>	upstream fan face	<i>up</i>	(fan) tip side

1.0 Introduction

Boundary layer ingestion (BLI)⁽¹⁾ is a propulsion integration technique that has the potential to improve aero-propulsive efficiency to achieve significant mission fuel burn reduction. Since the propulsive benefit of adding energy to the fluid is proportional to the added momentum, but the power required to increment momentum is (ideally) proportional to the square of velocity, increasing the momentum of the wake requires considerably less power than adding the same momentum to the undisturbed free stream⁽²⁾.

Within the APPU project^(3,4), an auxiliary BLI engine is investigated which provides between 10% and 15% of total propulsive force for an aircraft derived from an Airbus A321neo. In this context, a relevant question is how much propulsive force an efficient BLI propulsor should provide, considering that the remaining thrust is provided by conventional under-wing engines. Previous projects found that rear-fuselage BLI engines can achieve over 10% reduction in fan power requirement over comparable underwing turbofans⁽⁵⁾, and that this benefit increases for smaller propulsors and lower powers.

There is a strong similarity between most existing ducted propulsor concepts for rear-fuselage BLI and underwing nacelles, insofar as the flow travels through the nacelle almost

parallel to the engine axis, despite the conical flow on the upstream fuselage tailcone^(5,6,7,8). This causes a considerable length extension of the fuselage and creates a notable increase in surface area. There are indications, that this type of parametric design does not perform efficiently for low power and size⁽⁶⁾, due to the additional surface area and associated losses caused by adding the BLI propulsor. Since a given amount of power yields a higher propulsive force when applied to slower-moving fluid, it should be possible to design an auxiliary BLI propulsor which ingests only a comparatively small and slow-moving portion of the boundary layer which produces 10% of total thrust with an even less power required per thrust produced than bigger BLI engines, if it is designed accordingly.

One hypothesis is that the performance of small ducted BLI engines can be improved by not adapting the flow direction to the nacelle, but by adapting the nacelle design to the flow direction, i.e. aligning it with the conical flow on the rear of the fuselage tailcone. A single study was found which does not turn the incoming flow into an axis-parallel duct⁽⁹⁾, which is however not focussed on BLI nacelle design, and does not attempt to find an optimal geometry. For this reason, it was decided to create a parametric geometry which explicitly permits a conical design. The concept differs from both underwing nacelles and existing rear-fuselage designs in so far as it is submerged in the boundary layer, thus the Mach number in the flow around the nacelle is much lower than the flight Mach number, and the flow upstream of the intake is below the desired fan Mach number.

This study investigates the design space for such propulsors, finds design choices available in this context which may not be suitable for larger ducted fans that are (partially) exposed to free-stream conditions, and explores the relative benefit in energy consumption enabled by them, in comparison to previously-published BLI nacelles.

1.1 Theoretical Benefits of BLI and Definitions

The “classic” thrust and drag accounting rules⁽¹⁰⁾ allow separating thrust from drag, which in turn allows to minimize airframe drag and thrust-specific fuel consumption separately. In this context, Froude efficiency (equation 1) holds large explanatory power and practical value for the design of engines operating in free-stream conditions. Net thrust is equal to the momentum added by the propulsor, and since the inflow velocity and free-stream velocity are equal in this case, η_{Froude} only depends on free-stream and jet velocity, as shown in equation 1.

$$\eta_{Froude} = \frac{F'_N v_\infty}{P_K} = \frac{\dot{m} (v_{jet} - v_{in}) v_\infty}{\frac{1}{2} \dot{m} (v_{jet}^2 - v_{in}^2)} \Big|_{v_{in}=v_\infty} = \frac{2v_\infty}{(v_{jet} + v_{in})} = \frac{2}{\frac{v_{jet}}{v_\infty} + 1} \quad \dots (1)$$

For BLI engines, the definition of η_{Froude} cannot be applied in a straightforward way. The definition of overall net thrust by AGARD⁽¹⁰⁾ splits the flow field into a drag domain and a thrust domain, the latter comprising all streamlines which enter or exit the engine, with all forces acting on the drag domain making up the overall net drag, and all forces acting on the thrust domain contributing to (or subtracting from) thrust. According to this definition, all viscous forces acting on the fuselage would have to be regarded as thrust losses, although they should intuitively be classified as drag. In particular for small BLI propulsors whose contribution to propulsive forces may not exceed the fuselage drag, this results either in very small nominal thrust values which have no intuitive interpretation, or to large ambiguities in thrust definition, as one struggles to define *which* of the aerodynamic forces on the fuselage

should be classified as thrust and which as drag, in order to achieve some intuitively "correct" measure of thrust.

At least for simplified view of the flow, one might be tempted to use the inflow velocity into a BLI propulsor some small distance upstream of the propulsor, in combination with the jet velocity to define the thrust generated by the BLI engine. A closer read of power-balance methods⁽²⁾ should confirm that it is wiser to instead use the total conditions at the chosen upstream position and compute the velocity of the flow expanded to freestream conditions instead. This would lead to a thrust definition which appears to fit into equation 1:

$$F_{N,BLI,naive} = \dot{m}(v_{jet} - v_{in}) = \dot{m}(\Delta v) \quad \dots (2)$$

Inserting this "naïve" thrust definition into equation 1, however, can easily lead to η_{Froude} values larger than 1, which appears to violate energy conservation laws. This is a consequence of the fact that the a BLI propulsor can exceed the theoretical limit of thrust produced per power invested that applies to freestream engines, which is the very appeal of BLI propulsion. The reason is that the theoretical lower limit of power required to produce a given amount of forwards momentum produced is determined by the energy already contained in the flow on which the propulsor operates, which may be much less than in the freestream. The idealized power needed to impart momentum on the flow passing through the propulsor is given in equation 3.

$$P_K = \frac{\dot{m}}{2}(v_{jet}^2 - v_{in}^2) = \frac{\dot{m}}{2}(\Delta v^2 + 2v_{in}\Delta v) \quad \dots (3)$$

This means that the power required to add a given momentum Δv to the flow reduces with the velocity of the incoming flow, and with the specific momentum that needs to be added. Dividing equation 3 by equation 2 provides a simple equation for the minimum amount of power required per momentum desired. Although this does not result in a non-dimensional efficiency metric, it is still a useful construct, since it demonstrates how to reduce the power requirement for both BLI and freestream engines: Reduce specific thrust, and reduce inflow velocity.

Several alternative definitions of propulsive efficiency exist^(1,11), and while they do reflect some efficiency-related properties of a BLI propulsor, the fact that none of them can exceed 1 also means that they do not allow direct comparison to the η_{Froude} values of a propulsor operating in freestream, as an idealized BLI propulsor must be capable of surpassing an idealized freestream propulsor, whose upper efficiency bound is 1, in terms of the power invested for a given propulsive benefit.

1.2 Practical Considerations

For the design of BLI propulsors, there not currently any established methods. One occurrence of research into ducted BLI engine design seems to be that integrating a comparatively bulky nacelle at the tail end of an aircraft can be aerodynamically challenging, and the strong distortion in the inflow poses another challenge and likely causes some losses which reduce the benefit of installing a BLI engine in the first place.

This raises the question whether the challenge could be addressed by deliberately building a *smaller* BLI engine which only ingests part of the boundary layer, meaning that it does not have to accommodate the boundary layer flow as well as some portions of freestream inflow, as larger BLI engines often do^(12,13,14,15). Being immersed in the boundary layer, it would also

not need to be designed to avoid shocks on the outer surfaces to the some extent as underwing nacelles are. Since such an engine would operate on slower-moving flow than larger BLI propulsors, it would also be able to benefit more from the BLI effect, making it easier to negate any remaining adverse effects on the aerodynamic forces of the vehicle on which it is installed. In return, such a small engine would be limited in the amount of propulsive forces it can produce. This may be a very acceptable limitation in exchange for being smaller and easier to integrate with existing aircraft designs.

This study attempts a first design of such a small ducted propulsor for rear-fuselage BLI, with a focus on trying to align the airflow as much as possible with the flow on the "clean tailcone.

2.0 Methods

As comparison baselines, a "bare" fuselage and a conventional baseline BLI propulsor geometry were established. After that, a parametric geometry was defined in ParaPy, which also integrates the Meshing tool Salome SMESH and provides an interface to export meshes, boundary conditions and solver settings to ANSYS®Fluent®, which was used to perform RANS calculations. The outcomes of the calculations are flow fields as well as performance indicators, which were used to compare designs as well as evaluate the outcomes of a parametric study on the degree to which the BLI propulsor is matching the cone angle of the tailcone on which it is installed.

2.1 Application Case, Baseline geometry

The work presented here is adjacent to the APPU project^(4,3), which is concerned with the possibility of modifying an Airbus A321neo to replace the APU with a hydrogen-driven auxiliary engine which drives a BLI propulsor and contributes 10 to 15% of the total propulsive force. This is a somewhat lesser amount than needed to neutralise fuselage drag itself, and thus it is not necessary to "fill up" the entire fuselage wake, which should allow a BLI engine to use the power available to it in a very efficient way. While the APPU project focusses on an open rotor propulsor, this study investigates potential ways to design an alternative ducted propulsor, and whether magnitude benefits can be expected to be of similar magnitude as in other studies which regarded BLI engines which were larger in comparison to total power and/or thrust.

In order to avoid the necessity to conduct 3D flow simulations, the study regards an axisymmetric flow-field around a generic fuselage whose length and radius correspond to the A321neo fuselage (2m radius, 44.5m total length, 10 to 11 m tailcone length).

The "bare fuselage" and baseline geometries were derived from the results of the CENTRELINE project^(16,12), by multiple scaling steps:

1. scale down the geometry of fuselage and propulsor to match the 2m fuselage radius
2. adapt the length of the cylindrical portion of the fuselage to match the desired fuselage length
3. split the tailcone geometry at the inflection point
 - (a) extend the split fuselage with straight lines to generate the "bare fuselage" geometry

- (b) scale down the propulsor and rear tailcone geometry further, and connect it to the fuselage with a straight line, to generate the baseline design.

The scaling factor of the propulsor for the baseline design was adjusted iteratively until the simulations showed that the IPF with a fan pressure ratio (FPR) of 1.4. reached the desired magnitude, at cruise conditions. Figure 1 shows the scaled input geometry after step 2 and the "bare" and baseline geometries derived from it.

Figure 1. The scaled-down CENTRELINE geometry (blue), the bare fuselage geometry derived from it (green), and the baseline design for this study with a further scaled-down BLI propulsor

The bare fuselage drag was used to define the reference drag to compute IPF for all designs in the study, and the baseline design was used as an example for a "conventional" propulsor which is designed for a stronger engine, with the aim of ingesting a large part of the fuselage boundary layer.

2.2 Parametric Geometry Generation

The geometry definition was implemented in Python, using the ParaPy framework which implements CST curves⁽¹⁷⁾. An approach similar to Christie et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ was used in order to analytically construct CST curves which comply with constraints on points, tangents and curvature at different positions. Beyond the design variables, the only constraints applied to the geometry are tangency and curvature continuity on continuous surface curves. This avoids limiting the flexibility of the method through rules which appear intuitive but may prevent certain configurations, albeit at the cost of having to explicitly manage a larger amount of variables. The parametric setup and input parameters are shown in figures 3 and 4. Notable for for the parametrisation of the intake and exhaust duct and the nacelle geometry is that the angles at which the intake and exhaust duct wall meet the fan boundaries is fully variable, and the upstream part of the nacelle ("forebody") as well as the part downstream explicitly feature an inclination angle i , which allows conical geometries of intake and exhaust. The curves for intake, exhaust and outer nacelle aerolines are constructed in a coordinate system rotated by i , in order to avoid distortion that would result if the corresponding CST curves were constructed in non-rotated coordinates. Since both exhaust and intake feature a radial offset, and the tip radius of the fan domain at its upstream and downstream end are not necessarily aligned with i , the effective fan cowl inclination, i_{cowl} , may differ slightly from i . It is computed after the fact and indicates the angle between the symmetry axis and the nacelle chord line. The total

number of variables in the study is 26, although many of them were kept constant for most comparisons, and some were adapted only to avoid impossible geometries, or to keep certain properties of a design (e.g. the nozzle exit area) consistent within a study.

Figure 2. Overview of the different components and component curves of the parametric geometry

Figure 3. Parameters defining the fuselage, tailcone, fan and hub aerolines. Variables printed in black are inputs, variables in colour are results of geometrical relationships between different variables.

Since the ParaPy code represents each curve as a geometrical object in axisymmetric space, it is straightforward to conduct surface area or volume calculations on the geometry, and adapt the geometry according to the outcome. This was used to ensure that all designs provide at least the same tailcone volume as the reference case. In addition, a routine was implemented which can compute intake and nozzle area distributions, using a rolling-ball method. This analysis was however not linked to the geometry generation, thus only used for post hoc analysis in this study.

2.3 CFD method

The Parapy framework integrates the Python interface of Salome SMESH⁽¹⁹⁾, which allows defining a mesh entirely parametric in software. Since the geometry topology is comparably simple, it was chosen to implement a fully block-structured mesh for the parametric geometries. This was done by manually constructing curves and lines to define block boundaries, and defining objects which control the point grid point spacing along these boundaries, as well as tracking the number of points needed to ensure that opposite edges of structured blocks use the same number of cells.

The meshes are automatically exported, and a template is used to generate a journal file which triggers the correct solver settings, boundary conditions and convergence strategy in

Figure 4. Parameters defining the fan cowl and external nacelle aerolines. Variables printed in black are inputs, variables in colour are results of geometrical relationships between different variables.

Fluent. It was chosen to use a density-based CFD solver with a second-order upwind discretisation scheme and SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model. The air model is based on kinetic theory. The set-up of the boundary conditions uses a pressure far-field, a symmetry axis, a static pressure outlet for the fan face and a total pressure inlet for the rear face of the fan. In order to ensure both mass continuity and a user-defined fan pressure ratio (FPR), user-defined expressions are employed. These expressions define a target mass-flow for the fan face boundary to be equal to the massflow into the exhaust duct. Simultaneously, the total pressure on the exhaust side of the fan is derived from the mass-flow-averaged total pressure entering the fan, and the user-specified FPR. Total temperature on the exhaust side is computed from isentropic expression, using the mass-flow-averaged upstream total temperature and FPR. While this setup was found to lead to instabilities in the solver, they were addressed by setting a suitably-small under-relaxation factor for the target mass-flow adaptation on the fan face. This led to virtually-equal massflow into and out of the engine, thereby simplifying the calculation of thrust and drag forces.

The solver script also implements multiple convergence checks, on fan mass-flow, residuals, pressure and viscous forces on surfaces, as well as forces acting on the fan boundary and the fan power.

2.4 Performance metrics and Objective

In order to evaluate and compare different designs, a global quality metric is needed. A clean split between thrust and drag is however not possible in BLI configurations, and the very presence of the type of BLI propulsor regarded in this study already affects the aerodynamic forces on the fuselage. This means that "thrust" becomes an unreliable metric, and installation effects are tightly coupled to the design of the propulsor itself. For this reason, the performance metrics were chosen similar to the approach by Seitz et al.⁽¹⁶⁾, such that they directly reflect all costs and benefits caused by adding of a BLI propulsor. The cost is represented by the power applied to the fluid (P_{fan}), and computed as the sum of flux of total enthalpy across the fan face and exhaust inlet boundaries. The benefit is the streamwise force increment resulting from installing and operating the BLI propulsor on the airframe. It is calculated as the difference between the Net Vehicle Force (NVF , the integral of all surface and gauge forces acting

on the aircraft) on the respective geometry with installed propulsor and that on a “bare” airframe (equation 4). In order to keep nomenclature compatible with AGARD definitions⁽¹⁰⁾, we suggest the name “Installed Propulsive Force” (IPF, symbol Φ_{inst}). As a propulsive force, this paper defines Φ_{inst} positive in upstream direction, as shown in equation 4, while NVF is positive along the x axis (i.e. downstream) direction.

$$\Phi_{inst} = -(NFV_{inst} - NFV_{bare}) \quad \dots (4)$$

The comparison to a “bare” case implies additional work needed to compute installed propulsive force and introduces some uncertainty regarding how exactly the associated geometry should be defined. This means that Φ_{inst} is not an intrinsic property of a BLI design and includes a non-deterministic offset due to choices in defining the “bare” geometry. Nonetheless, this approach allows accurate comparison of different designs which use the same baseline geometry, and is most directly represents the net benefit of installing a BLI engine on an airframe, including all aerodynamic losses due to engine integration.

While the use of fan power and IPF as two separate performance indicators provides useful information, this approach complicates selecting the “best” among multiple designs unless one clearly dominates the others. The aim of engine design is usually to provide a pre-defined propulsive force, so one obvious way to compare designs is to constrain them to a constant, pre-defined IPF and compare the power required to achieve this. In the investigation at hand, since IPF is not known a priori, FPR was varied on some designs in order to adjust IPF to the desired value without changing geometry. Within the range of IPF found in the designs in this study, only minor adjustments were necessary, and the response was found to be very close to linear, which allowed linear interpolation from two solutions with different FPR to the exact IPF found for the baseline design.

For some designs, further metrics were investigated, namely the mass-flow-averaged total pressure in the highlight and nozzle plane, which allows computing the intake and exhaust duct losses.

2.5 Verification and Validation

A grid convergence study found that a cell count of 290×10^3 cells was sufficient to ensure that both the net vehicle force (NVF) and the predicted power imparted on the fluid by the fan (P_{fan}) were in the asymptotic range and deviated from the value predicted by Richardson extrapolation by less than 0.35% and 0.38%, respectively. A domain size study found that the effect of increasing the far field radius beyond 100 fuselage radii on (NVF) is well below 0.1%. y_1^+ was found to be below 0.9 on all walls.

Since experimental data, particularly for transonic rear-fuselage ducted BLI engines, is not available, the CFD process was tested against CFD results from the CENTRELINE project, using the un-scaled baseline geometry. The reference CFD data had been obtained using a different structured meshing process, using a third-order MUSCL scheme with a pressure-based solver. Due to use of the a body force model to represent the fan, the integral forces are not expected to match. Nonetheless, the intake mass-flow was matched to within 1%, and the total pressure profile at the fan face to within less than 1%, which confirms that the CFD process is sufficiently robust to model the type of flow at hand.

Figure 5. Mach number field around the bare fuselage (above) and the baseline PFC design

3.0 Results

Except for the bare fuselage reference and the baseline design, all designs were either generated manually or generated procedurally and adjusted manually. First, a number of designs were generated to test the robustness of the CFD process and to find values for most of the design variables which produce no obvious adverse flow phenomena, and to verify that the effect of FPR on IPF and P_{fan} was indeed linear within the relevant range. Then, a parametric study was undertaken to investigate the effect of i_{cowl} , while holding most other design variables constant.

The parametric sweep of i_{cowl} indicated notable advantages of designing the propulsor for higher cone angles than the baseline but also limitations which partially stemmed from the variables kept constant during the parameter sweep. For this reason, several additional designs were generated to make better use of the potential benefits of conical designs.

Finally, since the parametric sweep used fairly conservative intake and exhaust lengths, some designs were created which relaxed these constraints. While there are no established guidelines for the duct lengths needed for reliable off-design performance, these designs provide some indication on the importance of duct and fan cowl length, as well as the benefits made possible by aligning the propulsor geometry with the conical flow field.

3.1 Bare fuselage, Baseline design

The bare fuselage reference and the baseline design were created as described in section 2.1. The flow fields around the two geometries are shown in figure 5. It can be seen that the ducted propulsor in the baseline design is indeed completely immersed in the fuselage boundary layer. While an underwing nacelle would be expected to have transonic flow local supersonic regions on the outer surfaces at a flight Mach number of 0.78, the Mach number on the BLI the nacelle does not exceed 0.7. This is due to the low total pressure in which the BLI nacelle operates, as well as the increased static pressure at the base of the fuselage tailcone, which means that a profile curvature which could create locally supersonic flow results only in a slight Mach number increase over the already slow-moving flow in the fuselage boundary layer. By extension, this means that outer profile curvature for submerged BLI nacelles does not carry the same significance as it does in underwing nacelles⁽²⁰⁾, with regards to wave drag rise and limiting flight Mach number. The same phenomenon can be observed across all designs in this study (see also figure 8 for a more detailed view).

Table 1 lists the reference conditions and other properties of the bare fuselage and baseline cases. The same conditions were used for all other designs in the study, with the exception variations of FPR on some of the designs. The bare fuselage NVF was used as reference to compute IPF for all designs.

Table 1
Cruise condition and relevant aerodynamic forces on the bare fuselage and on the baseline configuration.

	bare fuselage	baseline
altitude	10650m (35kft)	
M (-)	0.78	
FPR (-)	–	1.4
NVF ^a (N)	9050	3916
IPF ^b (N)	–	5134
P_{fan} (MW)	–	1.186

^a NVF, like drag, is defined positive in downstream direction

^b IPF, as a propulsive force, is defined positive in upstream direction.

3.2 Conicity Sweep

The conicity sweep is based on a design which uses the same fan location and fan geometry as the baseline geometry, and also matches the baseline nacelle leading edge and trailing edge locations. This required an conicity angle of $i_{cowl}=6^\circ$.

Within the series, fan face location and geometry, intake and nozzle length and the cowl design variables were unchanged. The remaining variables were adjusted for each design to avoid undesirable features in the geometry, and to keep nozzle area approximately constant, in order to avoid affecting the fan massflow. Figure 6 shows the resulting geometries, and figure 7 shows the IPF and fan power of the designs, as well as for the baseline design. In order to determine the optimum, FPR was varied from 1.4 to 1.41 on the design with $i_{cowl}=11^\circ$, in order to gauge the rate at which power is converted to propulsive force, showing that this is indeed the design which can achieve the desired IPF with the lowest required power, requiring about 0.8% less power than the baseline. It can also be seen that the initial design of the conicity study, at $i_{cowl}=6^\circ$, performs very similarly to the baseline.

In order to create an indication of the performance of the BLI propulsor designs compared to a conventional engine, the theoretical limit power for a freestream engine was also computed, based on equation 1 for $\eta_{Froude}=1$, corresponding to an infinite actuator disk, with no installation effects. This is shown in figure 7 as a dashed line, and makes clear that the BLI effect provides the engines regarded in this study with a considerable advantage over freestream engines, although the data shown includes installation effects.

Another observation in figure 7 is that the line of P_{fan} over Φ_{inst} for small variations of FPR is almost parallel to the line representing the ideal freestream engine, but slightly steeper. This is due to the fact that an FPR increase causes an increase of the exhaust velocity, which gradually worsens the ratio of fan power momentum increase in the fan flow. As figure 5 shows, the jet Mach number is above the ambient value, which means that adding an increment to the exhaust velocity requires more power than it would if jet velocity was equal or smaller than freestream velocity.

Figure 6. Aerolines of some of the designs in the conicity parameter sweep. The full set comprises 10 samples at intervals of 1° from 6° to 15° .

Figure 8 shows the Mach number fields in several of the designs from the parameter sweep. It is clearly visible that a more conical design is better aligned with the flow on the tail of the fuselage, which reduces the need to turn the flow through the nacelle. In particular the exhaust duct straightens with increased conicity, removing the area of overspeed downstream of the nozzle plane. Similarly, the designs with higher conicity do not need to turn the flow into the intake duct, causing less overspeed. While the first design, with 6° conicity still shows a definite acceleration with following diffusion, from 12° upwards, the intake does not diffuse at all. This is also not necessary, given that the upstream Mach number is already below the desired fan Mach number. It is thus possible to create a much more even flow field, by aligning the intake with the inflow direction. The fact that the conical intakes accelerate the inflow slightly has the positive side effect of improving flow homogeneity, which in turn reduces distortion experienced by the fan.

Although the flow field around the propulsor appears to improve monotonically with conicity, the relationship between power requirement and IPF has an optimum at $i_{cowl}=11^\circ$. In order to investigate the cause for these, several other indicators were evaluated. Figure 9 shows the (massflow-averaged) total pressure in the highlight plane and the subsequent stations through the propulsor, and figure 10 shows the pressure losses in the inlet and exhaust duct, as well as the fan mass-flow. Since total pressure in the flow approaching the propulsor is already severely reduced, Inlet Pressure Recovery (IPR) is defined in this context as the ratio of total pressure at the fan face to the total pressure in the highlight plane, which marks the entrance to the inlet duct. Similarly Exhaust Pressure Recovery (EPR) is defined as the total pressure ratio between the downstream face of the fan (labelled `fan.out`) and the nozzle plane. It can be seen that total pressure in the highlight plane has a maximum at $i_{cowl}=11^\circ$, and although IPR improves monotonically with conicity angle, this is also the angle at which the fan receives the highest total pressure. The maximum of mass-flow at $i_{cowl}=8^\circ$, coincides with the the largest IPF in the series, which is plausible since massflow determines the momentum gain in the flow, with constant FPR and with only small changes in inflow total pressure. One reason for the reducing massflow at higher conicity angles may be that the static pressure around the exhaust increases as conicity increases, and a second reason is the fact that fan face geometry is kept constant for all designs, while the inflow angle into the fan face changes. The fan face

Figure 7. IPF (Φ_{inst}) and Fan power (P_{fan}) for all designs in the conicity sweep. For the design with $i_{cowl}=11^\circ$, FPR was varied, and the effect on IPF and P_{fan} is shown. The theoretical optimum for a freestream engine is shown for comparison.

area *projected in flow direction* is thus reducing as conicity increases.

The main loss factor for the conical nacelles at $i_{cowl} > 11^\circ$ thus seems to be upstream of the propulsor. The Mach number contours in figure 8 show a gradual reduction in Mach number of the flow upstream of the highlight plane. The reason for this is that the magnitude of highlight area was not controlled directly in the parametric study, and the designs with increased i_{cowl} have an increased highlight area. This leads to a widening pre-inlet streamtube, and thus to a slow-down in the flow with increased static pressure, which pushes the fuselage boundary layer closer to separation and causes additional losses. Another factor is that the steeper slope of the tailcone surface causes the tailcone surface area to increase, as can be seen in figure 6. While the plug surface shrinks considerably, the radial expansion of the tailcone leads to an overall increase of wetted area. Both of these aspects can be reduced by making further changes to the design, and this was exploited in subsequent designs.

3.3 Further improvements

Increasing the conicity angle of the propulsor allows the fuselage tailcone to have a steeper angle than in the baseline design. Since there is no necessity to keep the axial fan location constant, this means that the fuselage length may be reduced, thus reducing the wetted area.

In a first step, the best design from the conicity parameter sweep (with $i_{cowl}=11^\circ$) was changed by moving the fan face upstream by 0.37m, while adapting the curve connecting

Figure 8. Inlet pressure recovery (IPR) and exhaust pressure ratio (EPR), as well as the fan mass-flow as a function of i_{cowl}

Figure 9. Mass-flow-averaged total pressure in the highlight and exhaust nozzle planes (solid lines) and at both fan boundaries (dashed lines).

Figure 10. Inlet pressure recovery (IPR) and exhaust pressure ratio (EPR), as well as the fan mass-flow as a function of i_{cowl}

tailcone curve, but keeping all other shapes unchanged. In a second step, the intake length of the resulting nacelle was reduced, and the highlight area reduced from about 133% of fan face area to 125%, while keeping the intake area distribution convergent. For both designs, FPR was varied in order to confirm that the effect on IPF and P_{fan} is the same as observed in earlier designs, and to compute the power required to match the baseline IPF, which is 1.5% and 1.7% less than required by the baseline design, respectively. The performance metrics are shown in figure 11.

Shortening the tailcone is found to have a notably larger effect than reducing intake length, and mainly increases IPF, while leaving P_{fan} almost unchanged. This is consistent with the interpretation that the main effect of shortening the tailcone is a reduction of drag, which directly translates into an increase in IPF. Reducing intake length similarly provides an increment to IPF, though to a lesser extent.

A final design change further increased conicity from 11° to 12° and shortened the exhaust, which also reduced the nacelle surface area considerably. Figure 12 shows the geometry of this design, compared to the baseline design. The new design has 3m² less nacelle and intake surface area, 1.6m² less area on the exhaust plug, compared to a 0.8m² fan face area.

Figure 11. IPF (Φ_{inst}) and Fan power (P_{fan}) for all designs discussed in this paper. The two series labelled "shortened" are derived from the $i_{cowl}=11^\circ$ sample from the conicity sweep. The currently best-performing design investigated so far is highlighted.

The IPF and power requirement are shown in figure The new design has a power requirement 2.1% lower than that of the baseline design. 11 ("current best"), and figure 13 shows the Mach number distribution for both the baseline and the new design. It is clearly visible that, beyond reducing surface area and thus potential for friction drag, additional loss factors are reduced. Since the exhaust nozzle of the baseline design is pointing in axis-parallel direction, the flow has to be turned on the plug, causing an overspeed region which leads to additional friction. The intake of the baseline design contracts before expanding again, visible in the Mach number reduction in the downstream part of the intake duct. While not causing clearly visible losses, total pressure in the baseline intake reduces by 0.87%, compared to only 0.67% with the new design.

Both designs, however show a slow-down of the incoming flow upstream of the ducted propulsor, which is likely to be associated with total pressure losses. This is an indication that the highlight area may still be larger than would be optimal for the fan massflow. Another potential point for improvement is the nacelle boattail angle. The new design reaches fairly low Mach numbers on the outside flow near the trailing edge, and reducing the boattail angle, in conjunction with reduced curvature on the rear part of the nacelle, has the potential to reduce the effect.

4.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

The potential for small, submerged BLI engines to improve the efficiency of aircraft propulsion is significant. In the case investigated in this study, the power which the propulsor needs

Figure 12. Comparison of the baseline geometry and the best-performing design found during the study. The shape of the bare fuselage is shown in grey.

Figure 13. Mach number distribution around the baseline design (left) and the best-performing design found during the study (right).

to apply to the air in order to relieve the main engines of 10% of their thrust requirement at cruise conditions, was found to be 2.3% lower than the theoretical limit for any propulsor working in freestream conditions (i.e. $\eta_P=1$), a "bare" turbofan engine, even with very low specific thrust, has a η_P of around 80%. Installation penalties for modern underwing turbofan engines are in the order of 10% of "bare" thrust. In combination, this means that the fan on an underwing turbofan engine would need to apply 35% to 40% more power to the flow than the BLI propulsors discussed here, in order to achieve the same propulsive benefit. Even if the fan design for such an engine should require some compromises which degrade its efficiency by one or two percentage points compared to that of a conventional turbofan engine, the benefit of a small BLI engine is considerable, even if it should not be possible to supply more than 10% of total thrust in this manner.

Comparing the new designs found in this study to the reference BLI propulsor, it was found that a 2.1% reduction in fan power can be achieved, and further improvements are likely possible. There are several reasons why these gains can be achieved:

- By working only on the slower-moving parts of the boundary layer, the BLI effect is much stronger than for a bigger engine ingesting most of the boundary layer
- Since the ingested air is moving comparatively slowly, the intake does not need to diffuse, eliminating one source of losses and simplifying the design. The reference intake is diffusing, thus causing additional losses
- The fan cowl surrounding the propulsor is also immersed in the boundary layer, eliminating shock losses and reducing friction drag compared to an engine whose outside is

exposed to undisturbed flow

In terms of design strategies, it was found that rather than mimic ducted BLI engines found in published work, it is beneficial to align the ducts and the nacelle closer with the flow over the boattail of the fuselage, by increasing conicity and moving the fan upstream. Based on a parametric study and some manual adjustments, a reduction of required power of 2.1% over shapes typical for "conventional" larger BLI engine studies was found. This is because the conical propulsors help to reduce wetted area and avoid flow turning, which in turn reduces associated losses further. A further advantage was not object of the study but should also be mentioned: The conical propulsors take up much less space (creating fewer issues with ground clearance during take-off rotation) and are likely to be significantly lighter than propulsors designed after a more conventional template.

Further improvement is likely possible, and may be achieved by further increasing conicity and moving the fan upstream. At the extreme end, this may result in an almost unchanged tailcone geometry compared to the bare fuselage, although there may also be limits to the approach, either due to off-design performance or due because fan design for such a flow becomes infeasible. The design of an efficient fan for a converging conical duct is also the biggest unknown for the concept of conical BLI propulsors. Rotating turbomachinery functions well with conical ducts in which the fluid moves radially outwards, such as a conventional fan sitting on a conical spinner. Compressing air which is moving radially inwards may be more difficult to achieve efficiently. This aspect may limit the conicity or may limit the fan pressure ratio, as a function of conicity. It should be mentioned, though, that a modest efficiency penalty on the side of the fan may well be acceptable if the installation penalty can be reduced by several percent in return. Another limitation of designs with high conicity is that they are not necessarily suited to accommodate a conventional turbo engine core, since the plug starts directly at the rear fan face. This means that the fan must either be turned by an electric motor, or the engine must employ a different arrangement than mounting the fan on the engine axis upstream of the compressor inlet.

Further investigations are desirable, and based on the current set of results, the following avenues of research seem to hold the most appeal:

- Update the geometry definition to explicitly control intake and exhaust duct areas and area distributions, based on the expected massflow and FPR.
- Conduct a more comprehensive exploration of the potential design space. Further improvements to the design are likely possible, and the borders of the feasible design space have not yet been explored.
- Extend the CFD model to include a body force model which represents the fan in a more realistic way. This is expected to result in a reduced estimate of installed propulsive force for a given fan power, on the order of 1% or 2%.
- Expand the range of CFD analyses to off-design cases such as sea level static (SLS) and idle descent. To cover all relevant off-design conditions, including take-off and cross-wind, 3D simulations are necessary. It is not clear to what extent gusts would impact the design, and at least a few unsteady simulations to this end appear necessary to clarify this.
- Explore the ability of fans to function well in conical ducts which move the fluid radially inwards, and whether there are specific design changes which could prove helpful in this regard, either to the fan or the propulsor aerolines.

- Investigate a range of fan sizes, FPRs and target IPF. For the comparatively small values of IPF in this study, submerged BLI propulsors use less power than even a perfect freestream propulsor could. This means that, contrary to conventional turbofan engines, increasing mass-flow and reducing FPR does not always reduce energy use for BLI propulsors. Therefore, there must be an optimum size for a given IPF, and there must be a threshold for IPF above which a fully submerged BLI engine is no longer the most efficient option, and a larger fan (or open rotor) which also ingests air from outside the boundary layer becomes advantageous.

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